

LASER IMPACT GENERATION OF ULTRASOUND: APPLICATIONS TO THE CHARACTERIZATION OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

This work describes some recent advances dealing with the characterization of composite materials by using laser generated ultrasound techniques. Although the various acoustical modes (bulk, surface and plate) can generally be used, we restrict ourselves here to the discussion on bulk waves. One fundamental feature is that the propagation of transient divergent bulk modes in anisotropic solids is done at the group velocity. In the present work, wavespeed measurements are performed in several composite materials along numerous non-principal direction of propagation. Also discussed are wavefronts reconstruction and the possibility of predicting theoretical displacement fields using Cagniard de-Hoop method.

Keywords: Non destructive evaluation - Carbon epoxy composite - elastic constants -
Laser impact ultrasound - Phase and group velocities

1. INTRODUCTION

Laser generation of ultrasound facilitates simultaneous longitudinal and shear wavespeeds measurements in isotropic and anisotropic materials. The operating characteristics of thermoelastic ultrasonic point sources have been extensively investigated [1,2]. It is a broadband, repetitive and a non-contact source which is readily amenable to operation in a scanning mode. When combined with adequate optical detection schemes [3,4], this non contactness enables measuring acoustical wavespeeds at high temperatures, and this has been done for various isotropic materials [5,6]. Methods and models to describe the propagation of transient divergent waves obtained by laser impacting a solid have been borrowed from geophysics. In the simple cases of an isotropic half-space or plate, analytical expressions for the displacement fields are available. However, when anisotropy is taken into account, the determination of the theoretical displacement fields is an intricate problem which is still open. Such transient divergent waves in an anisotropic plate propagate at the group velocity [7]. Despite the fact that the displacement fields are generally unknown, it is yet possible to compute the arrival of the wave fronts of the different bulk multiple modes by using simple ray theory.

2. MEASUREMENTS OF ELASTIC CONSTANTS

Experimental work has been carried out with the aim of measuring the elastic constants of single crystals and composite materials [8, 9]. The very first precise measurements of the elastic constants of anisotropic materials using this method were reported in germanium single crystals by Aassel and Monchalin [8]. These measurements, performed along the principal directions, were quite accurate and compared well with published values. One important limitation of such an approach is that it necessitates various crystallographic cuts, often as many as there are independent elastic constants, i.e. three in the case of germanium which belongs to cubic symmetry. Furthermore, the application of this method requires the presence of the multiple bulk modes. This last point is not always satisfied for absorbing composite materials.

Another possibility is to utilize the fact that laser impact elastic waves are launched in various directions of a material, in either the thermoelastic or ablation regimes. These ideas have been applied to the measurement of the elastic constants of a silicon single crystal as well as a unidirectional composite material. These experimental efforts used scanning configurations [10], where the source is moved over the front surface of the specimen, while the detection is done by a point-like sensor mounted in a fixed position onto the rear surface. One difficulty of this approach is that the correct identification of the transverse waves is not a trivial matter. However, the wavespeeds measurements done in a principal plane (i.e. a plane containing two acoustical axes) were sufficient to utilize various versions of a specific inversion algorithm enabling to determine the elastic constants from wavespeeds measurements performed in numerous different directions of propagation [11]. The fundamental equation describing the propagation of elastic waves in solids has the form:

$$C_{ijkl}n_jn_k U_l - \rho v^2 U_i = 0,$$

where C_{ijkl} is the stiffness tensor, ρ the density of the material, $\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{k}/|\mathbf{k}|$ is a unit vector pointing along the direction of the wavenumber vector \mathbf{k} , U is the amplitude of the displacement vector (or polarization vector).

The characteristic equation associated with the above equation which provides the eigenvalues of the Green-Christoffel tensor, is in the general case cubic in terms of the elastic constants and of degree six as a function of the wavespeeds or cubic in v^2 . For instance, in the case of hexagonal symmetry (five independent elastic constants), the phase velocities of the two quasi-waves in a plane containing the sixfold axis of symmetry are given by the following equations [12]:

$$V_{qL} = \{(A + B) / 2 \rho\}^{(1/2)} ; V_{qT} = \{(A - B) / 2 \rho\}^{(1/2)}$$

where,

$$A = C_{11} \sin^2\theta + C_{33} \cos^2\theta + C_{44}$$

$$B = \{[(C_{11} - C_{44}) \sin^2\theta + (C_{44} - C_{33}) \cos^2\theta]^2 + (C_{13} + C_{44})^2 \sin^2 2\theta\}^{1/2}$$

Here θ is the angle the wave normal makes with the principal axis 1.

Moreover in an anisotropic solid, even in the absence of dispersion and attenuation, it is well known that there exists a geometrical transformation between the phase and group wavespeeds $v(\omega) = \omega / k$ and $V(\omega) = \partial\omega / \partial k$, as given by [12]:

$$V(\omega) = v(\omega) + k \frac{\partial v}{\partial k} = - \frac{\nabla_{\mathbf{k}} \Omega(\omega, \vec{\mathbf{k}})}{\partial \Omega / \partial \omega},$$

where $\Omega(\omega, \vec{\mathbf{k}})$ is given by $\Omega(v, \mathbf{n}) = \det |C_{ijkl} n_j n_k - \rho v^2 \delta_{il}| = 0$, with $\vec{\mathbf{n}}, v$ replaced by $\vec{\mathbf{k}}, \omega$ respectively. When this slowness surface presents an inflexion (i.e. a sign change in curvature) there exist cuspidal edges in the group velocity surface. The phase and group velocities are identical along principal directions as well as along some particular directions

called pure mode directions. Generally, for arbitrary directions of propagation, the two wavespeeds are different.

The laser used to make the measurements reported in this article was a Nd/YAG laser generating pulses 10 ns in duration at a repetition rate variable in the range 0.3 - 30 Hz, with a medium power output typically ranging from 7 to 70 mJ per pulse at a wavelength of 532 nm. The optical beam was focused down to a spot size of approximately 0.02 mm.

The signals coming onto the rear surface of the plate were detected with a miniature, broadband piezoelectric transducer whose aperture was 1.3 mm. Some characteristic signals obtained with such a system are shown on Figure 1 and 2 for two 1-D composites. On such waveforms one can always identify the wavefront arrival of the direct longitudinal wave (noted L), and in some cases (e.g. Figure 1a) the first multiple echoes labeled 3L. The transverse mode is clearly visible for the second composite and is shown with mark T. It should be emphasized that the correct identification of the transverse modes is not obvious to achieve. For instance, on the waveform dealing with the first composite at the epicenter configuration, the transverse waves arrivals are shown by arrows T₁ and T₂, but their precise determination was not done with the laser experiment, but instead by using an immersion system [13]. The wavespeed measurements were performed by using either correlation techniques or Hilbert transform between the narrowly filtered direct L (or T) mode, and the subsequent corresponding mode for successive observation angles. The absolute calibration timing of the experiment was done

Figure 1: Waveforms in a 1-D glass epoxy composite.
a) Normal observation angle (epicenter configuration).
b) 60 degrees observation angle (off epicenter configuration).

Figure 2: Waveforms in a 1-D carbon epoxy composite.
a) and b): Same captions as for Figure 1.

at the epicenter configuration by correlating the direct mode with its first multiple reflection.

The recovery algorithm in the 2-D case, which deals with the simultaneous inversion of quasi-longitudinal (qL) and quasi-transverse (qT) phase wavespeeds, has been described in Ref. [11]. Examples of such inversions are shown on Figure 3a and 4a for the two previous composites. In these Figures, the solid lines represent recovered group slownesses, and the direction of the fibers is along axis 3. The experimental data (shown as +) tend to be superimposed with the theoretical group slownesses, and this trend is unambiguous for the second composite. In this case, where the anisotropy becomes more pronounced (as compared to the first composite) the differences between phase and group velocities are significant and the inversion should definitely be made on group velocities [14].

3- WAVEFRONTS RECONSTRUCTION

When considering the propagation of bulk waves in an anisotropic plate, one might want to include not only the direct modes, but most of the subsequent multiple reflections going back and forth between the two surfaces. This is exactly what is physically happening, and only when dealing with an half space the restriction to the direct bulk modes is correct. In turn, and as was discussed in the previous section, one needs to construct the ray surfaces from the slownesses surfaces. Although the differences between group and phase velocities can be slight on the qL mode when the anisotropy is small because it has a constant sign in curvature, significant changes occur for the qT mode (for instance in principal plane {1,3} of the hexagonal symmetry) especially in the region of the cusps which correspond to points where there is sign inversion in the curvature of the slowness surface.

One might be interested in systematically probing the influence of such features. A significant step was recently done by recording and analyzing a very large amount of waveforms obtained during a unidimensional scanning experiment in silicon single crystal [7, 14]. In this work, the waveforms were obtained by using miniature piezoelectric transducers, and a pair of characteristic waveforms in composites are shown on Figures 1 and 2, both at the epicentre location, and at off epicentre. The numerous oscillations coming afterwards the arrivals of the qL and qT modes are not relevant features of the propagation but instead are artifacts due to the ringing of the transducer and are discussed further in [7].

Experiments involving 1-D scans, which uses a pulsed Nd:YAG laser source and a piezoelectric detection, were done with silicon single crystals. A simple but powerful signal processing method was then implemented, which consists in a false grey level coding of the data. Maxima (respectively minima) in the signal voltage were given a level of grey more closer to the black (respectively white) pixels which was proportional to the amplitude of the extrema. Thus the application of such a procedure resulted in scan images, and many examples are available in references [7] and [14], where the wavefronts are imaged versus the position of source impact. On such pictures one recognizes the multiple oscillations due to ringing of the piezoelectric transducer as alternances of dark and bright grey levels which are not relevant propagation features. Nevertheless, the different wave arrivals are still visible with this representation. For instance, the qL and qT wavefronts are clearly distinguished as well as some multiple reflections and modes conversions on the second interface. There are also features with singularities having cuspidal shapes. Confirmation of this last trend can be obtained by using a Monte-Carlo numerical code enabling computations of the various wavefronts based on propagation made at the group velocities. The results of such analysis are provided in [7, 14]. The identification of the main experimental features is unmistakable. The cuspidal singularities are present at the correct positions, and the presence of the head wave on the experimental waveforms was confirmed [7].

Other numerical approaches have been designed recently which involved for the theoretical predictions simpler algorithms than cumbersome Monte Carlo statistical routines. A convenient method to compute the group velocities it to develop the characteristic determinantal equation yielding the following dispersion relation:

$$\Omega(\omega, k) = (\alpha \frac{k^2}{\omega^2} - \rho) (\beta \frac{k^2}{\omega^2} - \rho) (\gamma \frac{k^2}{\omega^2} - \rho) - \frac{k^4}{\omega^4} \{ (\alpha \xi^2 + \beta \epsilon^2 + \gamma \delta^2 - 2\delta\epsilon\xi) \frac{k^2}{\omega^2} - \rho(\xi^2 + \epsilon^2 + \delta^2) \} = 0$$

Figure 3: Experimental results for the glass epoxy 1-D composite material
 a) Theoretical section of the ray surfaces in the plane (1,3) (---) and experimental data (+). The elastic properties of the material are the following:
 $C_{11} = 26.1$ GPa; $C_{33} = 65.5$ GPa; $C_{44} = 10.5$ GPa; $C_{66} = 8.50$ GPa;
 $C_{13} = 9.58$ GPa; $C_{12} = C_{11} - 2C_{66} = 9.31$ GPa; $\rho = 1.208$ g/cm³.
 b) Visualisation of the bulk and head wave theoretical wavefronts (---) in plane (1,3), and experimental data (+).

Figure 4: Experimental results for the carbon epoxy 1-D composite material

a) Theoretical section of the ray surfaces in the plane (1,3) (---) and experimental data (+). *The elastic properties of the material are the following:*

$C_{11} = 11.79$ GPa; $C_{22} = 12.31$ GPa; $C_{33} = 147.62$ GPa; $C_{44} = 6.61$ GPa;

$C_{55} = 6.00$ GPa; $C_{66} = 3.35$ GPa; $C_{12} = 5.54$ GPa; $C_{13} = 6.91$ GPa;

$C_{23} = 8.78$ GPa; $\rho = 1.500$ g/cm³.

b) Visualisation of the bulk and head wave theoretical wavefronts (---) in plane (1,3), and experimental data (+).

where the components of the Green-Christoffel tensor, in the case of the orthorhombic symmetry, are to be expressed by:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= C_{11} n_1^2 + C_{66} n_2^2 + C_{55} n_3^2 & ; & \quad \delta = (C_{12} + C_{66}) n_1 n_2 \\ \beta &= C_{66} n_1^2 + C_{22} n_2^2 + C_{44} n_3^2 & ; & \quad \varepsilon = (C_{13} + C_{55}) n_1 n_3 \\ \gamma &= C_{55} n_1^2 + C_{44} n_2^2 + C_{33} n_3^2 & ; & \quad \xi = (C_{23} + C_{44}) n_2 n_3 \end{aligned}$$

The group velocity is then obtained by computing the gradient of the slownesses in the wavenumber space normalized to the partial derivative with respect to the angular frequency. Further numerical details are given in [15] and in a forthcoming article by the same authors. Figures 3b and 4b shows a pair of characteristic results for the two composites already considered, when the qL and qT waves are taken into account. In each case, the arrival of the cuspidal features is recorded on the qT modes, i.e. on the branches labelled T and 3T for the first multiple reflection. The exact spatial position of such singularities, is evidently related to the group slownesses (see Figures 3a and 4a), meaning in turn that both representations are strongly linked. Also visible on Figures 3b and 4b are the arrivals of the so-called "head wave" or conical wave which exists beyond the critical angle on the transverse mode. This wavefront, arriving between the qL and the qT modes, is degenerated, on the qT mode at the critical angle, and on the qL mode at the grazing observation angle.

Figure 5: Cagniard de Hoop contours in the carbon epoxy 1-D composite.
a) 18.5 degrees observation angle (2 intersections with the real axis).
b) 30 degrees observation angle (4 intersections with the real axis).

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The use of bulk waves launched by laser impacting composite plates has shown great promises to probe the intricacies of anisotropy in such materials. Several problems still remain, for instance difficulties in designing simple and stable recovery algorithms of the elastic constants based on the measurements of group velocities. One further problem is to calculate the theoretical displacement fields by using Cagniard de Hoop methods, or any other numerical techniques. Some progress are undertaken at various institutions. The advantage of using semi-analytical methods such as Cagniard de Hoop is that it provides guidance in the treatment [16]. For instance, the so-called Cagniard de Hoop contours (see Figure 5) provides the information on the arrivals of the bulk waves, which are given by the intersections of the contours with the real axis. Figure 5a is taken just above the cusp (located on Figure 4a at 18.68 degrees).

Numerous authors have proposed using laser generated Lamb waves [17,18,19] and surface waves [20], but most of them did study isotropic solids. Surface waves seem to be promising due to the weak decrease of the amplitude of the wave with distance (as compared to bulk waves), but it is not so far evident that full recovery of the elastic constants is possible based on

these waves. Measurements of attenuation [21] has been achieved, and other experimental set ups were designed. A full account may be found in a reference book [22] (mainly applied to isotropic solids) and in a recently published review article [23].

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